

Boosting Behavior Tree Generation for Robots with Large Language Models and Genetic Programming

Aaron Verdaguer-Gonzalez Magí Dalmau-Moreno Luis Merino Néstor García
Robotics and Automation Unit Robotics and Automation Unit Service Robotics Laboratory Robotics and Automation Unit
Eurecat Eurecat Universidad Pablo Olavide Eurecat
Technology Centre of Catalonia Technology Centre of Catalonia Sevilla, Spain Technology Centre of Catalonia
Barcelona, Spain Barcelona, Spain lmercab@upo.es Barcelona, Spain
aaron.verdaguer@eurecat.org magi.dalmau@eurecat.org nestor.garcia@eurecat.org

Abstract—Mobile robots are becoming increasingly ubiquitous in modern society, requiring more human-like interaction capabilities, such as following operator instructions and collaborating with humans. Conventional robot programming methods often fall short in achieving these complex behaviors. Behavior Trees (BTs) offer a promising alternative due to their modularity, scalability and reactivity. We propose utilizing general purpose, system-prompted Large Language Model (LLM) assistants to decompose task descriptions into executable BTs, which are subsequently refined using Genetic Programming (GP) and a state machine like low-resource BT execution simulator, where they will be tested for task completion. This approach eliminates the need for fine-tuning LLMs, thereby reducing computational costs and saving time and energy. Our method successfully solves all proposed scenarios, enhances applicability across diverse environments, and democratizes behavior generation for non-experts, outperforming baseline methods in efficiency.

Index Terms—Behavior Trees, Large Language Models, Genetic Programming, Human-Robot Interaction, Simulation

INTRODUCTION

The increasing deployment of mobile robots in industries such as manufacturing, logistics, and healthcare necessitates advanced interaction capabilities to enable seamless collaboration with humans and adaptation to dynamic environments and unseen tasks [1]–[3]. Traditional programming paradigms, including Hierarchical Finite-State Machines and subsumption architectures, often struggle with flexibility and scalability, limiting their effectiveness in handling complex, open world scenarios [4]–[6]. Behavior Trees (BTs) offer a compelling alternative by structuring robotic behaviors in a modular and hierarchical manner, thereby improving reusability, readability, and adaptability [5], [7].

Large Language Models (LLMs) have recently emerged as promising tools for generating BTs directly from natural-language task description due to their vast amounts of world knowledge [8]. However, LLM-generated BTs often suffer from critical limitations, including hallucinations, misinterpretations, and the need for extensive fine-tuning on large datasets to ensure reliable performance [9]. Conversely, methods based solely on Genetic Programming (GP) provide structured optimization but suffer from lengthy search times and susceptibility to local optima [10].

To address these gaps, we propose a **novel pipeline that integrates LLMs with GP for BT generation**. Our approach leverages LLMs to create an initial BT from natural-language descriptions and refines it through GP within a low-resource simulation environment, eliminating the need for fine-tuning LLMs while enhancing efficiency and robustness. This work addresses whether an LLM-assisted pipeline, followed by GP refinement, generate robust and efficient robot behaviors without large-scale fine-tuning of LLMs can boost BT generation for autonomous agents.

By combining the adaptability and interpretability of BTs, the linguistic reasoning capabilities of LLMs, and the optimization power of GP, our framework accelerates behavior generation and improves applicability across diverse robotic tasks. To validate our approach, we present experiments demonstrating the effectiveness of our framework in both controlled and realistic simulation scenarios. This work contributes to the field of autonomous robots as follows:

- **Bridging LLMs and GP for BT generation** – We demonstrate a method that integrates LLMs for rapid BT synthesis with GP for structured optimization, reducing computational load while maintaining high adaptability. Our approach avoids the need for large-scale dataset training, making it more computationally and timely efficient.
- **Enhancing accessibility for non-experts** – Our method enables users with task specific knowledge but with minimal programming knowledge to generate executable BTs from natural language instructions.
- **Improving adaptability to previously unseen tasks** – The combination of LLM-driven BT generation and GP-based refinement ensures that generated behaviors generalize well across different tasks and environments.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. First, we delve into a comprehensive review of the literature surrounding the utilization of LLMs as behavior generators, as well as the application of GP in learning BTs. Then, we provide a detailed description of our proposed methodology, elucidating the intricacies of combining LLMs and GP for behavior generation in autonomous systems. We described the used benchmarking

scenarios and engage in a thorough discussion of the results obtained. Finally, we draw insightful conclusions from our experiments and propose directions for future research.

RELATED WORK

Our proposed approach integrates LLM-based BT generation with GP-based optimization. While both LLMs and evolutionary algorithms have been individually explored for BT synthesis, a combined approach has remained underexplored [11].

A. LLM Based BT Generation

Recent studies have investigated the use of LLMs for generating BTs from natural-language task descriptions. For instance, [9] introduced a Phase-Step prompt design to facilitate hierarchical BT task generation with behavior-tree-embedding-based search. While their approach enables cross-domain BT generation without requiring predefined primitive tasks, it is limited to sequential action plans and does not fully exploit the reactive control nodes in BTs.

Other approaches, such as LLM-BRAIn [12], involve fine-tuning LLMs on large datasets to improve BT generation accuracy. LLM-BRAIn, for example, generates robot BTs from operator commands but requires fine-tuning on 8,500 instruction-following demonstrations. While these models demonstrate promising results, their reliance on fine-tuning poses scalability challenges, particularly in domains where large labeled datasets are scarce.

A major limitation of LLM-based BT generation methods is the risk of producing logically inconsistent or hallucinated plans. Moreover, fine-tuned models often struggle with domain adaptation, requiring additional training for new environments [13]. Our work mitigates these issues by leveraging GP for structured post-processing, ensuring that generated BTs are both functionally valid and adaptable.

B. GP for BT Optimization

Evolutionary algorithms, particularly GP, have been widely used to optimize BTs. GP treats BTs as populations of candidate solutions, evolving them through genetic operations such as mutation and crossover. Previous works such as [10], [14] have demonstrated the effectiveness of GP in evolving BTs for autonomous agents, where candidate programs are evaluated based on task completion, execution efficiency, and structural complexity.

The GP approach proposed by Iovino et al. [10] employs a deterministic, low-resource simulator to refine BTs by minimizing execution time and structural redundancy. This method enables BT evolution in unpredictable environments but suffers from long convergence times, making it impractical for real-time adaptation. Our work builds on these efforts by introducing an LLM-assisted pipeline that generates an initial BT, significantly reducing the search space for GP. This hybrid approach accelerates BT optimization while maintaining the robustness of GP-based evolution.

Existing methods based purely on LLMs face challenges related to hallucinations, domain mismatches, and fine-tuning requirements. On the other hand, purely GP-based methods require extensive search time and struggle with local optima. Our proposed approach addresses these limitations by combining LLM-assisted BT generation with GP refinement, leveraging the strengths of both methodologies.

METHODOLOGY

Our methodology leverages LLM assistants created using OpenAI’s platform and GP to automate the generation and optimization of BTs for specific robotic applications. However, our approach is agnostic to the choice of LLM, meaning that any other suitable large language model could be used instead, provided it offers similar capabilities for natural language understanding and generation. The process is structured into distinct phases, ensuring that user provided high-level task descriptions are translated into valid and executable BTs, optimized for efficiency and readability as shown in Figure 1.

The approach is design to bridge the gap between natural task descriptions and automatic robust robot behavior generation. Hence, the process begins with the user defined assignment details, which is interpreted, structured and parsed through a pipeline of three LLM powered assistants. These assistants decompose the task into more meaningful components for the LLMs, parametrize the possible leaf nodes and generate an initial BT structure which is validated for its correctness and executability. The validated BT is then refined using the GP approach proposed in [10], ensuring efficiency and readability before deployment into a real robot. Realistic robotic simulator environment such as Gazebo [15] or AI2Thor [16] are used to validate the full pipeline.

The first step in our approach employs a hierarchical prompting strategy [17], where each assistant plays a specific role in breaking down the proposed problem. An example of an interaction with such agents can be seen in Figure 2 The assistants and their functionality are as follows:

- 1) **Task Understanding Assistant (TUA)**: Extracts essential entities such as objects, locations, and task constraints from user input, ensuring clarity and reducing ambiguity for further steps. Extracted details are confirmed with the user before proceeding.
- 2) **Node Parametrization Assistant (NPA)**: Transforms the structured task description into parametrized BT nodes, consisting of actions (e.g., "move to location/object" to "move to pick table 0"). This assistant uses RAG [18] when necessary to incorporate relevant examples from past tasks, improving consistency.
- 3) **Behavior Tree Assistant (BTA)**: Synthesizes an initial BT structure based on the previously generated nodes, leveraging hierarchical decomposition. This ensures modularity, readability, and reusability.

By following this structured pipeline, the assistants generate a coherent and well-defined BT, reducing the need for manual intervention and accelerating the development process.

Fig. 1. Workflow of the proposed approach.

(a) First interaction with the Task Understanding Agent (TUA). (b) Initialization of the Node Parametrization Assistant (NPA).

Fig. 2. Example of the Validation Engine correcting hallucinations and logical inconsistencies in a LLM generated BT.

Despite the advantages of LLM-generated BTs, they are prone to hallucinations and logical inconsistencies. To address this, the Validation Engine performs a thorough examination to correct potential flaws before further refinement. The validation process includes grammar checking, ensuring adherence to formal BT syntax rules, execution feasibility detecting and correcting unreachable or illogical action sequences as depicted in Figure 3, and redundancy removal, optimizing the BT architecture by eliminating unnecessary nodes. This ensures that despite the BT not ancestrally completing the task, it is syntactically correct, logically sound, and ready for further optimization.

Once the BT is validated, it undergoes GP optimization to enhance its efficiency and adaptability as proposed in [10]. This evolutionary approach refines the BT based on performance evaluations in a low-resource simulator before final testing in Gazebo or AI2Thor. As depicted in Figure 1, the GP process involves a BT population initialization derived from the LLM pipeline. A fitness evaluation where each BT is executed in a low-resource simulator, where its performance is scored using a cost function J :

$$J = R - (\alpha \|s_d - s\|^2 + \beta b + \gamma T)$$

where,

- R represents the reward for task completion.

- $s_d - s$ measures the deviation from the desired state.
- b is the BT size, penalizing unnecessary complexity.
- T is the execution time, encouraging efficiency.
- β and γ represent importance coefficients.

BT selection and reproduction where tournament selection [19] is used as well as the most successful BTs are selected based on their fitness scores. Crossover and mutation are used as genetic operators to introduce structural variations to improve adaptability. The convergence criteria consists in repeating the process for N generations or until performance improvements plateau and task is completed.

Our approach embodies a framework that combines LLM-driven BT generation, validation, and GP-based optimization to create adaptable robotic behaviors. It ensures:

- **Executability:** LLM-generated BTs are validated against structural and logical constraints.
- **Efficiency:** GP-based refinement minimizes complexity and improves execution speed.
- **Generalizability:** The approach is scenario-independent, capable of handling diverse tasks.
- **Accessibility:** By removing the need for LLM fine-tuning, it democratizes robot programming for non-experts and users with low computational resources or time.

Through this systematic integration of AI-driven task decomposition and evolutionary optimization, we provide a robust solution for autonomous robot behavior generation in deterministic environments as shown in the provided link¹ solving the first synthetic scenario in Gazebo.

EXPERIMENTS

We evaluated our framework in controlled synthetic scenarios proposed in [10] and two randomly-selected realistic task-based environments extracted from ALFRED [20], assessing its ability to generate and refine adaptive, efficient, and readable Behavior Trees (BTs).

¹Link to the video.

Fig. 3. Example of the Validation Engine correcting hallucinations and logical inconsistencies in a LLM-generated BT.

C. Synthetic scenarios

We first tested our approach in three progressively-complex environments, where a robot manipulates cubes across tables, see Figure 4.a:

- **Scenario 1:** A cube always appears on a fixed table, requiring simple pick-and-place execution.
- **Scenario 2:** The cube spawns randomly, introducing uncertainty.
- **Scenario 3:** Multiple cubes appear at once, demanding multi-object coordination.

D. ALFRED

To assess generalization, we tested the framework on ALFRED, a benchmark for natural language-driven household tasks [20], to extrapolate from more synthetic scenarios to more realistic tasks. Two simple pick-and-place tasks were selected, an example of Task 1 can be seen in Figure 4.b:

- **Task 1:** Place a baseball bat on a bed.
- **Task 2:** Move a watch to a glass table.

E. Genetic Programming Modifications

To test if performance of the GP algorithm could be further improve, we implemented several modifications to the original GP approach, which evolves BT structures using structural constraints inspired by [5]. Unlike [10], where mutations were limited to nodes of the same type, our approach introduced greater diversity in mutations, ensuring broader exploration of possible BT solutions. The GP algorithm autonomously selects condition nodes, preserving essential decision-making logic at an atomic level. The proposed mutations are:

- **Change Mutation Probabilities:** Adjusted mutation rates to prioritize changes within nodes of the same type, maintaining structure while promoting meaningful variations.
- **Allow Condition Nodes:** Allowed the last child of a subtree to be a condition node, increasing flexibility in execution logic.
- **Global Alignment (GA):** Implemented Needleman-Wunsch-based crossover, aligning parent BTs and selecting the most structurally similar regions to combine.

(a) Gazebo environment for synthetic scenarios.

(b) AI2Thor environment for ALFRED scenario 1.

Fig. 4. Environment examples, where the generated BTs were tested.

- **Custom GA Approach:** Designed a custom similarity matrix based on node proximity, function, and parameterization, ensuring crossover occurs between behaviorally related nodes.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

When looking at Figures 5.a, 5.b and 5.c, Scenario 1 cost reduction happens quickly, with most methods improving significantly within the first 1,000 generations. Our pipeline (solid red line) reaches a low cost rapidly and maintains it, outperforming others in both speed and final cost. While other methods converge eventually, they fall short of ours in efficiency and performance. Scenario 2 shows a slower,

Fig. 5. Average results for the different experiments where lower cost implies better performance and dashed lines denote the task is not solved yet.

more varied cost decline, indicating higher task completion complexity. Some methods fail to solve tasks, as shown by dashed lines. The proposed methodology remains strong, achieving low costs with minimal fluctuations.

The most challenging synthetic scenario shows a slow cost reduction and many unsolved tasks even after 8,000 generations. Methods diverge significantly, some plateauing early. Despite this, "Ours" stays robust, consistently achieving low costs and outperforming others in handling complex tasks. Across all scenarios, our approach outperforms others in speed, task completion, and cost efficiency. Its robustness stands out, especially as scenario complexity increases, with no other method matching its effectiveness.

Figure 5.d compares the cost reduction over generations for two different ALFRED tasks, where lower cost implies better performance. The original method (violet) starts with a high cost and gradually decreases, but many instances (dashed lines) fail to solve the task. In contrast, the proposed method (red) begins with a lower cost and converges much earlier, indicating greater efficiency. The solid lines in the red approach show that it consistently completes tasks, whereas the original method fluctuates more and takes longer to stabilize. Overall, the proposed method significantly outperforms the original, achieving faster convergence and more reliable task completion in more realistic scenes.

While our approach successfully automates robotic behavior generation, some limitations remain and must be acknowledged. Our method partially relies on a hand-crafted state-machine like low resource simulator. This implies domain specific knowledge and might require some modifications to such simulator which can only be done by an expertise. Although Large Language Models (LLMs) interpret high-level task descriptions, they depend on structured input and may struggle with ambiguous instructions. User-provided parameters (e.g., specifying manipulable objects and task constraints) must be correctly defined for optimal BT synthesis.

Additionally, while our validation engine effectively filters out syntax and structural errors, it does not fully eliminate high-level logic inconsistencies. LLMs can still introduce hallucinated responses, such as unnecessary or incorrect steps,

which the validation engine might not detect if they remain logically plausible within the task context. Future work could enhance validation by incorporating semantic reasoning models or reinforcement learning based verification.

Despite these limitations, our approach lowers the entry-barrier for non-experts, enabling behavior generation via natural language rather than requiring manual BT programming. This significantly enhances the usability of robotic automation systems, allowing users to specify tasks in intuitive terms without needing expertise in robotic behavior or control systems. A key strength of our framework is its modular nature, since it consists on clearly distinct components making it highly adaptable. As we have shown, we can plug in different GP algorithms or optimization algorithms as well as different LLMs as assistants, including fine-tuned models if desired.

We believe that this approach can be extended in many different directions. For instance, removing the state-machine-like simulator but keeping the low computational cost when testing and computing the costs of BTs with a different simulator could increase real-world scalability, making it applicable to dynamic, noisy, or partially observable robotic tasks. Also, the evolution of the LLM-based BT generation pipeline is possible using a CoT-like approach, reducing even more domain specification and improving generalization for more partially observable or open world problems. Further improvements include the possibility of testing and computing the BTs in a stochastic environment, demonstrating that this approach can also generate very robust trees for more complex scenarios.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we proposed a LLM-assisted BT generation pipeline that integrates LLM-based task decomposition with GP optimization to create adaptable and efficient robot behaviors. Our approach significantly reduces the manual effort required to design BTs, making behavior generation more accessible to non-expert users while improving adaptability in uncertain and multi-object environments.

Through extensive experimentation, we demonstrated that LLM-generated BTs provide strong initial solutions, requiring

minimal corrections in structured tasks. Our method also generalized well to real-world-inspired tasks in the ALFRED benchmark, confirming its scalability for natural language-driven robotic behaviors. Next steps include expanding to more complex tasks and diverse simulation environments, validating the pipeline on physical robots, enhancing human-in-the-loop interactions for better non-expert usability and real time behavior modification, and extending the BT framework to manage sensor-driven conditions and uncertainties in dynamic settings and open world settings. Ongoing tests aim to automate the testing of our approach across the entire dataset.

Beyond the autonomous robotics domain, our approach has significant implications for manufacturing, collaborative robotics, and home-assistant applications. By enabling natural language-based programming of robotic behaviors, our method bridges the gap between human task specifications and executable actions. This paves the way for more intuitive and adaptable robotic systems in both industrial and domestic settings while democratizing behavior generation so that a broader range of users can create and refine behaviors without extensive AI or programming expertise. As we explore scalability, real-world deployment, and human interaction, our research lays a strong foundation for adaptive, user-friendly robot control frameworks across diverse environments.

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